

Pioneer Starter Soccer Simulation 2D Team Description Paper 2024

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Abstract. Soccer 2D games are known worldwide, and in Iran, they are known as IranOpen Robocup. This year marks the 18th anniversary of this competition. It involves two football teams, with the main source being WorldModel, and 11 players participating in a 6000-cycle game. The roles are the same as in real football.

Keywords: 2d Soccer Simulation, Robocup, IranOpen, Functions

1 Introduction

For the second time participating in RoboCup competitions, we have focused on developing the team's shooting and passing abilities. We have also added pressing and blocking tactics. Our team members have been studying other teams' TDP to improve the Pioneer team. In this paper, we will share some information about the improvement of the Pioneer team and the new functions that we have added. After making these changes, we hope to achieve better scores.

1.1 Team History

Pioneer team is soccer simulation coding team that is attending the competitions for the second year now. The members have been studying programming for 3 years along side other great teams and mentors. Our team has been focusing on improving our old codes and ideas. In this file we have explained our source and new ideas.

Opponent name	Results	Team name
Hermes	1-4	Pioneer
Black Warning	0-4	Pioneer
Alpha	1-2	Pioneer
Hypatia	0-4	Pioneer
Hades	0-6	Pioneer

Table 1. The team's results from IranOpen 2023 competition

2 Bhv_BasicMove

The bhv_basicmove file includes many functions, two of these functions being “block” and “press” which have the overall same purpose which is stopping the opponent from gaining full control over the ball.

2.1 Press

In the “press” function, we obtain the coordinates and the distance to the nearest opponent using the following commands:

```
const PlayerObject *op = wm.getOpponentNearstToSelf (5, true);  
double dist_op = wm.getDistOpponentNearestToSelf(5, true);  
Vector2D op_pos = op->pos();
```

Next, we evaluate certain parameters. For instance, if the opponent's distance from me is greater than 10, or if the distance between the nearest teammate and “op_pos” is less than 3, or if the ball-to-me distance is less than

“dist_op”, the function returns “false”.
Otherwise, it moves toward “op_pos” and queries the opponent.

2.2 Block

In the “block” function, the process is quite similar. However, the key difference lies in finding the coordinates and distance to the second nearest opponent to the ball after locating the nearest opponent. This is achieved using the following commands:

```
const PlayerObject *next_opp = wm.getOpponentNearestTo(oppon, 5,
&dist_oppon);
double dist_next_opp = wm.getDistOpponentNearestTo(v_oppon, 5);
Vector2D v_next_opp = next_opp->pos();
```

Subsequently, by comparing various parameters, such as "if my distance to the ball is greater than 15, or if the distance between the nearest teammate and the ball is less than my distance to the ball, or if the time it takes for a teammate to reach the ball is less than that of the opponent," the function returns “false”. Otherwise, the second player closest to the ball is positioned to block the opponent's pass.

2.1 Positioning

Upon learning that the positioning system using Fedit was not permissible, our team had to make a strategic adjustment to the "new_position" function. We opted to use a two-dimensional list for the players and a traditional list for the ball number. This allowed for a more precise identification of the target's x and y coordinates by matching the ball number and player number to their respective indices. Additionally, we integrated a dedicated function, "ball_num", to facilitate this process.

```
rcsc::Vector2D Bhv_BasicMove::new_position(const rcsc::WorldModel & wm, int
unum)
{
    Vector2D target;
    int num = ball_num(wm);
    double pos_x[56][12]={...};
    double pos_y[56][12]={...};
    target.x = pos_x[num][unum];
    target.y = pos_y[num][unum];
    return target;
}
```

(the "..." are replacements for the list's content)

The above code consists of two two-dimensional lists, each assigned to coordinate vectors, for the purpose of facilitating quick and efficient access to the target's x and y coordinates. The lists contain an equal number of members as the division of the field, which includes the 56-number field, meaning that, for example, if the field is sectioned into 56 areas, each two-dimensional list will include 616 numbers. The number of members per list is based on each player's 11-number representation.

In order to find the ball's area number, we created a dedicated function, "ball_num", which allows for seamless identification of the closest area to the ball.

```
int Bhv_BasicMove::ball_num(const rcsc::WorldModel & wm)
{
    Vector2D ball_list[56] = {...};
    int result = 0;
    for (int i=1; i <= 50; ++i)
    {
```

```

        if (wm.ball().pos().dist(ball_list[i]) <
wm.ball().pos().dist(ball_list[result]))
            result = i;
    }
    return result;
}

```

(the "..." are replacements for the list's content)

The "ball_num" function utilizes a regular list to contain an equal amount of numbers as the division of the field. This function searches through each area of the field and identifies the one closest to the ball using a "for" loop. When it finds an area that is closer to the ball than the current closest one, it updates the current result to reflect this and returns the value back to the "new_position" function.

3 Bhv_BasicOffensiveKick

3.1 Execute

In this part of the code bhv_basic_offensive_kick.cpp, we planned to separate the field into three parts.

First part: `wm.ball().pos().x >= -52.5 && wm.ball().pos().x < -36`

Second part: `wm.ball().pos().x >=-36 && wm.ball().pos().x < 36`

Third part: `wm.ball().pos().x >= 36 && wm.ball().pos().x <= 52.5`

This division allows us to apply different instructions in different parts of the game. For example, when defending, we can use "press" as our primary instruction for the players. When attacking, "shoot" can be the main focus. Based on our knowledge of the opposing teams, we can adapt our strategy accordingly. For instance, when facing strong teams, we may prioritize defensive orders to minimize potential losses. Conversely, when facing weaker teams, we can aim for a victory with more goals. In the middle part of the field, a specific type of shot is used. It targets a sector the width of the goal and, if unopposed, results in a powerful and fast shot. This approach has two potential outcomes: 1. If successful, our team scores. 2. If unsuccessful, the ball is moved away from our goal, benefiting our

team.

Fig. 2. In the left image the field is separated into three separate parts and the right image separates the field into 2 sections, with an imaginary line to change the priorities in the execution and to be able to have suitable tactics depending on the ball placement. The number of sections or the placement of these imaginary lines can be easily changed in the game source at any time and might not always be consistent.

3.2 Pass

The "pass" function is called in the `bhv_basic_offensive_kick.cpp` file when the player has the ball and the ability to pass it to another player. The result of this function is a boolean value, which determines whether the player was able to pass to another player or if the execution should move on to the next function. The code begins with a simple list of all players or "targets" to whom we can pass, while avoiding counting ourselves as a target. It then prioritizes the list based on factors such as the distance of the targeted player from our goal and the opponent's goal, as well as the x value of the player. If there are no targets in the list, "false" will be returned, and no passing will occur. Then, the list is further prioritized using a set of simple "if" conditions. If there are no opponents in the circle between us, the ball, and the targeted player, the pass takes place using the `Body_SmartKick` function, and a "true" value is returned. The rest of the execution will not be checked.

3.3 Pass Short

In this part of the code `bhv_basic_offensive_kick.cpp`, we plan to make adjustments to the short pass strategy. These changes are different from the Base pass in the following ways: 1- The power of the pass will be divided into three parts based on the distance between the player and the best target: a) Less than 10 b) Less than 20 c) Less than 30 If the distance is more than 30, the pass will return false. 2- The sector ensuring that an opponent isn't in the way will be smaller when the distance between two players is low, and the speed of the ball is high, reducing the risk. 3- This pass will not allow the player to pass backward, preventing the ball from getting closer to our goalie. 4- Players that are too close to our goalie (less than 10) will not be included in the target list for passing, ensuring that the ball doesn't get close to the goalie.

3.2 Shoot

This function, similar to the three previous functions, is also in the `bhv_basic_offensive_kick.cpp` file, returning a boolean value. The general idea behind this function is somewhat similar to our regular pass function: creating a list of targets and prioritizing them based on various factors. In this case, the distance between the player and different

parts of the opponent's goal is considered. Using a simple "for" loop, the code goes through the opponent's goal. The goal is separated into 11 sections, with the x value consistently being 52.5 and the y value changing between -5 to +5. which it would be like this in our code :

```
for (double i=-5;i<=5 ;i++){  
    cuurent_goal= Vector2D(52.5,i);  
    DistFromGoal = cuurent_goal.dist(ball_pos);
```

```

Sector2D goal_triangle = Sector2D (ball_pos,1,DistFromGoal + 3, (cuurent_goal
- ball_pos).th()-10, (cuurent_goal - ball_pos).th()+10);
If (!wm.existOpponentIn(goal_triangle,3,true)) {
best_goals.push_back(cuurent_goal);
}
}

```

If there isn't any opponent in the triangle between the player, the specific goal section, and the ball, the y value of that section will be pushed back to the target list. If this list is empty, suggesting all sections of the goal are being protected by an opponent, the function will return "false," and no further action will be taken. Otherwise, the list will be prioritized based on our distance to every section; the closest target will be selected as the best target. As the code above says:

```

for(unsigned int i=1;i<best_goals.size();i++){
DistFromGoal = goalia_pos.dist(best_goals[i]);
if(DistFromGoal > best_dist) {
best_target = best_goals[i]; best_dist = DistFromGoal;
}
}
}

```

Using the "body smart kick" function and returning the "true" value, the code of this function ends.

Fig. 3. The white arrows on the left image represent each possible target for shooting the ball, although the number of arrows can be easily changed in the code's "if" loop. More sections will result in a more accurate chance of a successful shot. The red arrow on the right image is the selected target for the shot; as you can see, the red arrow doesn't have any deviation since a straight line is the closest trajectory for the ball.

3.3 Better Shoot

In the "Shoot_Better" section of the code, we adjust the shooting strategy based on the player's position and the presence of opponents. By prioritizing the furthest corner from the goalie as the primary shooting location, we create more space to shoot and widen the options available. Additionally, areas with opponents are fully closed off for shooting. Furthermore, we refine the power and speed of shooting based on the player's distance from the goalie it will get separated making sure the ball won't stop by friction of ball and land which includes this part of the code:

```

if(wm.getDistOpponentNearestToSelf(5) <2 ){

Body_SmartKick(best_target,2.7,2.7 ,1).execute(agent);
}
if(ball_pos.dist(best_target) <= 25 && ball_pos.dist(best_target) > 18){
Body_SmartKick(best_target,3,3,2).execute(agent);
}
if(ball_pos.dist(best_target) <= 18 && ball_pos.dist(best_target) > 10){
Body_SmartKick(best_target,2.5,2.5,1).execute(agent);
}
if(ball_pos.dist(best_target) <= 10 && ball_pos.dist(best_target) > 1 ){
Body_SmartKick(best_target,2.25,1.25,1).execute(agent);
}
else{
Body_SmartKick(best_target,3,2,2).execute(agent);
return true;
}

```

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